

SRI AUROBINDO GHOSH: SEVEN STEPS OF KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract:

This research paper delves into the philosophy of education propagated by Aurobindo Ghosh, Aurobindo Ghosh's philosophy of education, commonly referred to as integral education, emphasizes the development of the individual's spiritual dimensions. This paper explores the Sri Aurobindo Ghosh framework of seven steps or stages of development that an individual can go through in their spiritual evolution.

Key Words: Spiritual dimension, Knowledge, Self-realization

Introduction:

Aurobindo studied in England and as such he was very much influenced by Western philosophy and culture. But after returning from England, he made a deep study of the Indian literature and philosophy. He reconciled divergent ideas of Indian spiritual idealism with Western secular materialism. Hence, he created a metaphysical synthesis reconciling spirit and matter. According to Kenneth L Deutsch, 'The revolution that Aurobindo pursued was a spiritual revolution . His was a moral and spiritual task. This task is grounded upon three basic concepts of his philosophy— Sachchidanada or the Supreme Reality, Supermind or the Truth— consciousness and Evolution.' During his detention as an under-trial political revolutionary in 1908, Aurobindo underwent a spiritual transformation by having some mystical experiences, which had a profound influence on his mind and thinking. He came to realize that spiritual power, Sri Aurobindo Ghosh outlined a framework of seven steps or stages of development that an individual can go through in their spiritual evolution. These steps are often referred to as the "Seven Steps of Knowledge" or the "Seven Stages of Transformation." They represent a progression towards higher consciousness and self-realization. Yoga teaches us about the mechanism of body, mind, and spirit called Pancha Kosha Viveka (पंच कोष विवेक), which means knowledge of the five layers of our existence.it can be called the model of the human being or the conceptualization of the human being, which is called Pancha-kosha-vishleshana

अन्नं प्राणो मनो बुद्धिर्- आनन्दश्चेति पञ्च ते । कोशास्तैरावृत्तः स्वात्मा, विस्मृत्या संसृतिं व्रजेत्

॥१.३३॥

Annam praanah manah buddhih ānandah iti pañca te, koṣā taih aavritah svātmā vismritiyā
samsritim vajet (1.33)

Panchadasi

Sri Aurobindo's framework of the Seven Stages of Transformation outlines the spiritual evolution of an individual towards higher consciousness and self-realization. Here's an overview of these steps:

Physical Consciousness (Annamaya): At this stage, consciousness is predominantly focused on the physical body and its needs. The awareness is limited to the material world and its necessities. physical consciousness (Annamaya Kosha), Aurobindo recognized the significance of the actual body during the time spent training. He accepted that the body isn't simply a vessel for the brain or soul yet assumes a functioning part in molding encounters and learning.

Aurobindo underlined an all-encompassing way to deal with instruction that includes supporting the actual body through legitimate consideration, exercise, and wellbeing. He accepted that a solid body gives major areas of strength for scholarly and profound development.

His instructive way of thinking proposes that actual training ought not to be restricted to simple actual activities or sports. All things considered, it ought to envelop rehearses that fit the body, psyche, and soul. This could incorporate yoga, reflection, breathing activities, and exercises that advance a fair way of life.

Aurobindo's vision of instruction expected to stir and coordinate all components of human life, and the actual viewpoint was viewed as an essential piece of this comprehensive methodology. He didn't advocate dismissing the actual body in quest for scholarly or otherworldly turn of events yet rather looked for a decent and coordinated development of all parts of being.

Vital Consciousness (Pranamaya): Moving beyond the physical, this stage involves the development of emotions, desires, and vital energies that drive actions. It encompasses passions, desires, and the pursuit of pleasure. vital consciousness (Pranamaya Kosha) in training is established in his comprehensive comprehension of human instinct. The crucial cognizance addresses the existence power or energy that vitalizes the actual body and is related with feelings, wants, drives, and motivations. With regards to training, Aurobindo underlined the need to channel and change the imperative energies in helpful ways. He perceived that feelings and wants assume a critical part in shaping human way of behaving and learning. Rather than smothering or refuting these fundamental motivations, Aurobindo pushed for their figuring out, refinement, and diverting towards higher points.

Aurobindo accepted that schooling shouldn't just zero in on scholarly turn of events yet in addition address the close to home and volitional parts of an individual. Coordinating crucial cognizance into training includes developing capacity to understand individuals at their core, compassion, mindfulness, and a feeling of morals and values.

He proposed that educators ought to direct understudies in figuring out their feelings, wants, and energies and assist them with figuring out how to emphatically tackle these energies. By coordinating practices like reflection, care, and moral schooling, people could figure out how to deal with their crucial driving forces and use them in helpful and amicable ways.

Aurobindo's way to deal with schooling including essential cognizance focused on perceiving the significance of feelings and wants in human existence and coordinating these energies towards self-awareness, moral turn of events, and the advancement of society. This

coordination of the fundamental perspective inside instruction pointed toward cultivating a reasonable and incorporated development of the person.

Mental Consciousness (Manomaya): The stage where intellectual faculties develop, involving reasoning, logic, and analytical thinking. It's characterized by the ability to conceptualize, plan, and think abstractly. mental awareness (Manomaya Kosha) in schooling digs into the domain of comprehension, keenness, and the powers of the psyche. For Aurobindo, the psychological part of cognizance is fundamental for scholarly turn of events, thinking, investigation, and the procurement of information. With regards to instruction, Aurobindo underlined the need to go past repetition learning and remembrance. He pushed for a more unique and all-encompassing methodology that empowers decisive reasoning, inventiveness, and the investigation of different viewpoints.

Aurobindo accepted that schooling shouldn't simply zero in on gathering data yet ought to focus on the advancement of higher resources of the brain. This incorporates the capacity to address, reflect, combine data, and show up at unique bits of knowledge.

His instructive way of thinking proposed that educators ought to urge understudies to connect effectively in the educational experience. This includes invigorating interest, encouraging an affection for learning, and giving a climate that permits to the free and innovative articulation of thoughts.

Aurobindo likewise stressed the significance of incorporating the intellectual capacities with different parts of cognizance, like the essential and profound aspects. He accepted that a balanced schooling shouldn't compartmentalize these viewpoints yet rather encourage their amicable turn of events.

Aurobindo's way to deal with mental cognizance in schooling was focused on sustaining the mind, advancing decisive reasoning, and empowering a more profound comprehension of oneself and the world. This approach pointed toward empowering people to amass information as well as apply it imaginatively and morally in different parts of life.

Psychic Consciousness (Vijnanamaya): This stage involves connecting with the inner self or the soul. It includes empathy, intuition, and a sense of inner purpose and direction. Psychic consciousness (Vijnanamaya Kosha) in schooling dives into the most profound quintessence of a person's being — the deepest center that rises above the psychological, imperative, and actual aspects. In Aurobindo's way of thinking, the mystic awareness addresses the inward soul or the otherworldly quintessence inside every person. It exemplifies a feeling of genuine self, instinct, soul, and an intrinsic feeling of good and bad. Concerning, Aurobindo accepted that taking advantage of the mystic cognizance was fundamental for all encompassing turn of events. He underscored the significance of self-disclosure and interfacing with one's deepest pith as a primary part of schooling.

Aurobindo pushed for a type of schooling that urges people to investigate their internal identities, pay attention to their inward voice, and adjust their activities and figuring out how to their most profound desires and values. This approach includes practices like thoughtfulness, contemplation, self-reflection, and moral and otherworldly lessons.

For Aurobindo, instruction that incorporates the advancement of the clairvoyant awareness goes past scholarly or scholastic pursuits. It includes sustaining a feeling of direction, inward direction, and an ethical compass that coordinates people towards a satisfying and significant life.

Aurobindo's viewpoint on mystic cognizance in schooling underscores the significance of going past the surface layers of astuteness and feelings to find and line up with one's inward truth. This approach expects to cultivate a feeling of genuineness, reason, and moral lucidity in people's lives, forming their scholarly development as well as their general prosperity and commitment to society.

Spiritual Consciousness (Anandamaya): Transcending the individual self, this stage involves a connection with the universal spirit or divine consciousness. It is marked by a sense of unity, peace, and spiritual fulfillment. Spiritual consciousness (Anandamaya Kosha) in schooling addresses the apex of his comprehensive methodology, underscoring the acknowledgment of solidarity with the heavenly and a definitive motivation behind human life.

In Aurobindo's way of thinking, profound cognizance rises above any remaining degrees of awareness. It includes a consciousness of the interconnectedness of all presence and an acknowledgment of one's heavenly nature.

With respect to, Aurobindo accepted that a definitive objective ought to be to work with the enlivening and development of profound cognizance in people. He underlined that schooling shouldn't just zero in on scholarly, profound, and actual turn of events yet additionally on supporting the otherworldly part of an individual.

Aurobindo supported for a school system that assists people with finding their internal godliness, cultivating practices like reflection, thought, supplication, and the investigation of otherworldly texts. He accepted that these practices would empower people to interface with their higher selves, have internal harmony, and foster a feeling of solidarity with all creatures.

His instructive way of thinking proposed that educators shouldn't just give information yet in addition act as guides, helping understudies in their profound journey. This includes establishing a climate that upholds the investigation of more profound existential inquiries, empowers self-revelation, and works with the improvement of excellences like empathy, love, and benevolence.

Fundamentally, Aurobindo's viewpoint on otherworldly awareness in schooling underscores the significance of rising above individual limits and understanding the heavenly pith inside oneself and all creation. This approach expects to cultivate a feeling of profound satisfaction, inward congruity, and a more profound comprehension of the interconnectedness of all life.

Divine Consciousness (Chit): At this stage, one experiences a profound unity with the divine, becoming a channel for divine will or purpose. There's a sense of being an instrument for higher spiritual forces.

Sachchidananda: A definitive stage addresses a condition of unadulterated presence, cognizance, and happiness, where the singular cognizance consolidates totally with the heavenly cognizance.

Sri Aurobindo Ghosh's way of thinking of Sachchidananda addresses a definitive reality in his profound vision, consolidating presence (Sat), cognizance (Chit), and rapture (Ananda). With regards to instruction, Aurobindo's vision reaches out past customary scholastic figuring out how to include the all encompassing improvement of people.

Sat (Presence): Aurobindo accentuated that schooling ought to assist people with understanding their actual presence, going past shallow personalities and constraints. It includes figuring out one's motivation, potential, and interconnectedness with the world. Schooling, in this sense, turns into a course of self-revelation and self-acknowledgment, permitting people to unfurl their genuine self.

Chit (Cognizance): Schooling, as per Aurobindo, ought to extend cognizance. It includes the obtaining of information as well as the improvement of higher resources of the brain. This extension envelops decisive reasoning, inventiveness, instinct, and a more profound comprehension of oneself and the universe. Aurobindo imagined a school system that expands cognizance to see past the material and worldly, associating people with higher bits of insight and intelligence.

Ananda (Euphoria): Aurobindo accepted that schooling ought to at last prompt a condition of internal delight and satisfaction. It's about scholarly pursuits as well as about supporting a feeling of concordance, love, and euphoria inside people. Instruction, when lined up with the quest for Ananda, includes cultivating ethics, values, and practices that achieve a condition of internal happiness and ecstasy.

Aurobindo's vision of Sachchidananda in schooling advances an all-encompassing methodology that coordinates the physical, essential, mental, mystic, and profound aspects. It underscores the improvement of scholarly ability as well as the capacity to understand people on a profound level, moral qualities, otherworldly development, and a feeling of interconnectedness with all life.

Conclusion

These stages portray a singular's excursion towards self-acknowledgment, profound development, and a more profound comprehension of presence, at last prompting a condition of solidarity with the heavenly or extreme reality. The stage where scholarly resources create, including thinking, rationale, and scientific reasoning. It's portrayed by the capacity to conceptualize, plan, and think uniquely. This comprehensive training, as indicated by Aurobindo, empowers people to carry on with intentional existences, contribute genuinely to society, and eventually experience a feeling of internal satisfaction and concordance.

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